

Parental Academic Support and Student's Reading Motivation: A Mixed Method Approach

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Abstract. This study explored the significant relationship between parental academic support and the reading motivation of senior high school students. In this study, the researcher selected 200 senior high school students in the San Isidro District in Davao del Norte as the study's respondents in the quantitative phase. In comparison, ten students were selected for IDI and FGD in the qualitative phase. A mixed-method research design using an explanatory sequential approach was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean and Pearson-r Correlation Analysis. Findings revealed that parental academic support and reading motivation of senior high school students in San Isidro District in Davao del Norte were rated as extensive. Evidently, correlation analysis proved that there is a significant relationship between parental academic support and reading motivation of senior high school students in San Isidro District in Davao del Norte. The thematic analysis confirmed the extensive ratings on parental academic support and reading motivation of senior high school students in the San Isidro District in Davao del Norte. Thematic analysis showed that the reasons, homework assistance, expectations and values, and emotional support confirmed the significant relationship between parental academic support and reading motivation of senior high school students in San Isidro District in Davao del Norte.

KEY WORDS

1. Teaching English
2. parental academic support
3. explanatory sequential approach

Date Received: July 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: August 01, 2024 — Date Published: September 2, 2024

1. Introduction

Reading is a fundamental skill that underpins success in almost every subject. Students motivated to read are more likely to comprehend complex texts, expand their vocabulary, and perform better in exams and assessments. Students can gain insight into different cultures, perspectives, and life experiences through reading. This cultivates empathy, understanding, and tolerance for others, promoting a more compassionate and inclusive society. To foster reading motivation in students, educators and parents can encourage and support their reading habits, provide access to diverse and engaging reading materials, create a positive reading environment, and celebrate reading achievements. By nurturing a love for reading early on, students are more likely to reap the numerous benefits throughout their lives. In global issues, several types of research indicate that lack of motivation to read remains a perennial concern

among adolescent students worldwide (Brown et al., 2016). Park and Kim (2016) reported that students are disengaged in the learning process due to a lack of motivation to read, leading to lower academic achievement and disinterest in education. In addition, Ullah and Fatema (2014) reported that a lack of motivation can lead to decreased effort and engagement in academic, professional, or personal pursuits. This often results in subpar performance and an inability to achieve one's full potential. Also, lack of motivation can contribute to frustration, apathy, and low self-esteem. It may also lead to symptoms of anxiety and depression as individuals struggle to find purpose and meaning in their actions. On the contrary, Hayikaleng (2016) asserted that motivated readers are internally driven to read because they find joy, satisfaction, or personal fulfillment in the act of reading. They do not rely solely on external rewards or incentives to engage with books. Also, Alhamdu (2015) noted that motivated readers are persistent in their reading habits. They are willing to tackle challenging texts, push through difficult passages, and continue reading despite obstacles. Likewise, Chinappi (2015) indicated that motivated readers are more engaged in learning. When students are excited about reading, they actively participate in discussions, ask questions, and seek additional resources to deepen their understanding of the subject matter. On one hand, Cadosales et al. (2017) noted that parental support is a crucial factor in a student's development and academic success. It refers to the active involvement, encouragement, and guidance parents provide to their children's educational journey. When parents actively engage in their children's education, students are likelier to have better grades and overall academic performance. Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) highlighted that parental encouragement fosters a positive attitude toward learning, making students more receptive to education. Likewise, Owen (2016) found that Stu-

dents who experience consistent parental support are more likely to pursue higher education and succeed in their careers. Parents involved in their children's education and providing consistent support contribute significantly to their academic achievement, personal growth, and well-being. In the Philippines, Bustamante and Dequito (2018) reported that the NAT results of elementary and high school students showed a declining achievement level. The Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of students dropped from the school year 2007-2008, which posted an MPS of 49.26 percent to 47.40 percent in 2008-2009 and down to 46.30 percent in 2009-10. Indeed, it was emphasized that the reason for such poor performance in NAT is the students' reading problems. Moreover, Gunobgunob-Mirasol (2019) mentioned that the reading motivation of Filipino students seemed to decline as they approached higher learning and that reading motivation can be associated with the low performance of the students in English subjects and other related subject areas. Many studies focused solely on quantitative data, such as surveys or standardized tests, to assess reading motivation. While these approaches provide valuable insights, they might miss the nuanced and context-specific factors influencing students' reading motivations. Mixed-method studies, combining quantitative data with in-depth qualitative data (interviews, focus groups, etc.), could offer a more comprehensive understanding of the topic. Thus, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte, using a mixed-methods approach. Specifically, the researcher used a sequential-explanatory design to better understand the student's reading motivation as determined by parental support, which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding reading motivation in the context of students in the San Isidro District, Davao del

Norte. The results of this study may be of interest to other researchers as they could provide valuable knowledge for their research.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed mixed methods in this study, specifically explanatory sequential research design. This evolving research technique promotes the systematic synthesis or mixing of quantitative and qualitative data within a single study or ongoing investigation or inquiry (Creswell, 2013). This method collects and analyzes quantitative and qualitative data and integrates data during data collection, analysis, and discussion. This method uses procedures that implement quantitative and qualitative components concurrently (Creswell, 2017). According to West (2012), in sequential explanatory design, the qualitative data helps explain or build on the initial quantitative results in the explanatory sequential method. The explanatory sequential approach was a two-phase mixed methods design that explains and enriches the quantitative findings; thus, it elaborates the quantitative results by collecting qualitative data from participants chosen from the respondents of the quantitative phase. Sometimes, there were insufficient arguments that quantitative or qualitative may not be resolved by it, and sometimes each provides different pictures (Creswell, 2017). In the quantitative phase, the researcher specifically used the descriptive correlation approach to address the problems in the study and achieve its purpose. This approach measures two or more relevant variables and assesses a relationship between or among them (Schmitz, 2012). The relationship between online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency was described and examined. In the qualitative phase, the researcher used a phenomenological approach. A phenomenological study describes the ordinary meaning for several individuals of their lived experiences of a concept or phenomenon and focuses on their common experiences (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Phenomenology is the most appropriate approach because the researcher wants to understand the lived experiences of senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte (Creswell, 2017). Moreover, the quantitative data based on the survey questionnaires on parental support and learner's reading motivation was first collected and followed by the qualitative data based on the focus group discussion (FGD) and in-depth interview (IDI). This means a more dynamic and absolute understanding is possible than the use of only one data source alone (Creswell, 2013). Likewise, this method was used to compare, confirm, cross-validate, or corroborate findings, equally prioritizing the quantitative method. The researcher analyzed the survey data quantitatively and the FGD and IDI qualitatively to determine if the qualitative findings elaborated the quantitative findings (Creswell, 2013). Hence, this design was appropriate for purposely supplementing one method with the strengths of another (Creswell, 2013). Specifically, the quantitative component involved descriptive and correlational approaches.

2.2. Research Respondents—Quantitative Phase. The study's respondents were the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Division of Davao del Norte. In this study, the 200 respondents were selected through a strati-

fied random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling was a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the study's respondents. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those bonafide enrolled senior high school students, and who voluntarily signed the ICF and parental consent were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the socio-economic status of the students. Qualitative Phase. The researcher purposively selected five students for the in-depth interview (IDI) and five students for the focus group discussion (FGD). A total of 10 senior high school students from San Isidro District, Davao del Norte, were invited as participants. The Inclusion criteria used were bonafide senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. It was also considered that the numbers of males and females were well represented. Purposive sampling was apt for the qualitative participant selection of this study because, according to Daymon and Holloway (2011), it was a technique wherein a sample

The instrument's second part is about the reading motivation of the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. This questionnaire was adapted from Komiyama's (2013) Motivation for Reading En-

was chosen based on their features or characteristics, which enables detailed exploration and understanding of the constructs under the study and research questions. As Miles et al. (2014) denoted, purposive sampling is well suited to in-depth qualitative studies.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study used two sets of instruments: one for the quantitative phase and one for the qualitative phase. A panel of experts subjected these questionnaires to content validity testing and underwent pilot testing to test their validity and reliability. The experts' comments, corrections, and suggestions were incorporated into the final revisions of the questionnaires. Quantitative Phase. In the quantitative phase, the study employed questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The first part of the instrument focused on the parental support received by the senior high school students in San Isidro District Davao del Norte. This questionnaire was adapted from the study of Cadosales et al. (2017) and indicated the time students spend with their parents, parents' ways of discipline, and parents' involvement in school. The Cronbach alpha value for this instrument is 0.965, described as excellent, denoting the high reliability of the items. In answering the questionnaire, the items were modified to suit the context of this answer and be answerable using a 5-Likert scale: 5–Strongly Agree 4–Agree 3–Somewhat Agree 2–Disagree 1–Strongly Disagree. To determine the extent of parental academic support, the researcher used the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations presented below.

glish Questionnaire (MREQ), which indicated intrinsic motivation, extrinsic drive to excel, extrinsic academic compliance, extrinsic test compliance, and extrinsic social sharing. The Cronbach alpha value for this instrument is 0.922,

Range of Mean Descriptive Levels and Interpretations of Parental Academic Support

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	Parental academic support is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Parental academic support is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Parental academic support is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Parental academic support is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Parental academic support is never observed.

described as excellent, denoting high reliability of the items. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items were modified so that they may suit the context of this and be answerable using the 5-Likert scale: 5–Strongly Agree 4–Agree 3–Somewhat Agree 2–Disagree 1–Strongly Disagree. As a guide in determining the extent of student’s reading motivation, the researcher used a range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below.

Range of Mean Descriptive Levels and Interpretations of Reading Motivation

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	Reading motivation is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Reading motivation is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Reading motivation is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Reading motivation is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Reading motivation is never manifested.

Qualitative Phase. The researcher conducted an IDI and FGD with 17 senior high school students using a semi-structured interview. The use of the semi-structured approach was essential to discover new themes that emerged during the interview. As Bryman and Bell (2011) described, it was flexible and less rigid than structured. The researcher made an interview guide composed of open-ended questions to probe the participants’ lived experiences about parental support about learners’ reading motivation. Also, the researcher probed how these experiences shape their beliefs, attitudes, and motivation in learning. This interview guide had undergone content validation by three experts in the field of education. Their comments, corrections, and suggestions were incorporated in the final revisions of the questionnaires.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—

The researcher underwent steps in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire.

Quantitative Phase

Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the Schools Division Superintendent and then to the school principals of the selected public secondary schools in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. To obtain permission to conduct the study from the selected schools in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte, the researchers personally brought the letters to the principals of the schools where the study was conducted. The researcher initially appeared in the office of the principals and school heads last November 2022 to carry the letters asking permission to conduct the study. The principals accepted the letters. However, the principals reminded the researcher that during the study, the Division Superintendent's protocols should be strictly followed. This includes the lack of disruption of classes and the health protocols in relation to the COVID-19 crisis. After this, the researcher proceeded to distribute and retrieve the survey questionnaires. **Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire.** The researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. The questionnaires were distributed in the third quarter of S.Y. 2022-2023. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the researcher conducted the study face-to-face. However, the questionnaire was distributed following health protocols. The study respondents

were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. **Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data.** After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Then, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS. **Qualitative Phase** For the qualitative data collection, IDI and FGD were conducted to gather the participants' lived experiences about the students' reading motivation after the invited participants had emailed back the signed ICF. Regarding the conduct of the IDI and FGD, the researcher reflected in the ICF that the process had to be recorded. Only those invited participants who could email back their signed ICF were scheduled to join the IDI and FGD. Also, the researcher ensured that her schedule was most convenient for the participants. Using the validated open-ended questionnaire, she had to limit the IDI and FGD sessions to 30 to 40 minutes. In addition, she discussed thoroughly the ethical considerations to the participants. Also, the participants' perspectives on the phenomenon of interest were revealed according to how they viewed it and not as the researcher viewed it. Also, since the interview involved a personal interaction where cooperation was essential (Creswell, 2013), the researcher who acted as the interviewer saw to it that she had a good rapport with the interviewees by using a non-threatening stance during the IDI. Likewise, for the FGD, the researcher sent an email or text through messenger to confirm the availability of the participants who signed up to join the FGD at the time scheduled for the FGD Google Meet session. An invite was emailed at least two days before the scheduled FGD session. The researcher acted as the facilitator during the FGD and stimulated the discussion or brainstorming through sensibly chosen guide statements prepared beforehand and validated by a panel of experts. Participants in the FGD were informed

prior to the submission of the signed ICF that the whole session was going to be recorded.

2.5. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—To establish the study’s trustworthiness, the researcher followed the four proposed criteria for evaluating interpretive research work by Lincoln and Guba (1985): credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. This study’s trustworthiness was addressed through a thorough data collection by survey and in-depth interview, supported by FGD for triangulation. **Credibility.** To ensure the credibility of this study, the researcher adopted a well-established research method. The researcher recognized the importance of incorporating correct operational measures for the concept that was being studied. Credibility was achieved by ensuring that the source of the data was credible. The researcher also ensured the honesty of the participants by giving them a chance to refuse to participate in the study. Also, the researcher ensured the quality of this study by carefully adhering to the protocols set by the Rizal Memorial Colleges Graduate School; the process flow in data collection, data analysis, and data integration were carefully reviewed, ensuring quality and dependability. **Transferability.** The researcher addressed transferability by providing readers with evidence that the research findings could apply to other contexts, situations, times, and populations. Transferability is concerned with the extent to which the study’s findings can be applied to other situations (Creswell, 2013). The readers had to note the specific details of the situations and methods to compare them to a similar situation familiar to them. **Dependability.** To address the dependability issue more directly, the researcher made sure that the process within the study was discussed in detail, thereby enabling future researchers to repeat the work, if not necessarily to gain the same results or findings of the study. For the readers to gain a thorough understanding of the methods and their effectiveness, the researcher included sections such as the research design and its implementation, described what was planned, and how they were executed on a strategic level. The researcher described the operational details of data collection, addressed the details of what has to be done in the field, and provided a reflective appraisal of the project, evaluated the appropriateness of the process of the inquiry that was being undertaken. With the guidance of her mentor and evaluation of the expert panelists, all activities were correctly done; as a result, stakeholders and the readers can be assured of the study’s dependability. **Confirmability.** To safeguard the accuracy of the transcription and initial interpretation of the data, IDIs and FGD were recorded, and the transcriptions were subjected to the participants’ responses review. The process included in Creswell (2017), steps and procedures in analyzing qualitative data known as the last stage in validating the accuracy of the information; through this method, the researcher assured confirmability of the findings of the study (Creswell, 2017). As such, the researcher used an audit trail of raw data, analysis notes, process notes, personal notes, and preliminary developmental information to achieve confirmability. In other words, the researcher’s findings were derived from the survey responses and narratives of the participants in the IDI and FGD.

2.6. *Ethical Considerations*—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The

survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher asked for the participants' permission through a written informed consent form. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were given to them so that they could better understand the reason for their participation and choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that participants' involvement in the study is voluntary. If they refused to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the participants. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote senior high school student's reading motivation and may contribute to the enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The study participants are teachers, so they are not considered vulnerable since all of them are of legal age, and they are not considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey would be set at the participants' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the participants, who would be the real source of information, to protect the identities of the respondents. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the consent of the participants. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed, access was limited to the researcher alone. To protect the participants' privacy, it was assured that the researcher is the only person that could access the Google Form and survey done through social media. After

the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the online survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the real source of information. Risk, Benefits, and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. The participants, without restrictions, could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide that was used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the participants of the study. Likewise, this study is designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher made sure that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire online. The participants were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all participants equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the respondents for the study. Anybody who fits the qualifications of being bonafide senior high school students in the purposively selected schools. During the conduct of the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting as little time as possible

to the routine of the respondents. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any type of communication in relation to the research was done with honesty and transparency. To safeguard the welfare of the participants, the researcher properly implemented the methods that are discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Importantly, the researcher described the extent of the involvement of the respondents in this study and shared how the researcher maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the study results. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that any other factor, like conflict of interest, did not influence the responses of the participants. The study's findings could be accessed by the respondent's parents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the In the study, the Division of Davao del Norte was given a furnished copy of the research results

2.7. Data Analysis—Quantitative Phase
The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing parental support and the learner's reading motivation. It was also used to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (parental academic support) and dependent (student's reading motivation) variables. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r .

Qualitative Strand The data from the IDI and FGD were analyzed using thematic anal-

so that the respondents could access them and use them for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the participants in a conducive environment and learning materials which were ample and available in the study and were done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the participants was ensured by properly encoding the ratings of the participants during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was good practice to involve the community during every phase of research, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement would be accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate method to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

ysis. The interview was recorded so that data and notes that were obtained could be analyzed to determine the emerging codes and themes. This method emphasizes pinpointing, examining, and recording patterns or themes within data. Themes are patterns across data sets that are important to the description of a phenomenon and are associated with a specific research question (Mertens, 2018). In the thematic analysis, the researcher first read and re-read the transcripts to become familiar with the data. The data were organized in order to generate initial codes. Codes reduced ideas into smaller chunks of meaning. Codes were examined and grouped according to themes. Themes were formed and reviewed, modified, and devel-

oped. The themes were coherent and distinctive from each other. Lastly, the identified themes were defined in order to identify their meaning (Creswell, 2017). After the data collection, a detailed step was applied to analyze the data.

Sequence, Emphasis, and Mixing Procedures This study employed a sequential collection of quantitative and qualitative components. However, data integration happens during the analysis and interpretation phase. **Sequence.** A sequential-explanatory mixed-method design was used in this study. This means that the data that was gathered in the quantitative strand was further verified in the qualitative strand to explain the salient results of the survey. For the quantitative strand, the researcher collected the data online through adapted questionnaires and interviews of the learners in the public elementary schools in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte with a validated interview guide for the qualitative phase. This means that the survey and interview were conducted separately and simultaneously. The qualitative data verified the quantitative data for cross-validation or confirmation of findings. With this method, the qualitative results determine the depth of the quantitative findings of the study. **Emphasis.** The quantitative data were given more emphasis in the study because they used empirical tools and provided substantive support for the qualitative findings. The findings were integrated during the interpretation phase of the study. The sequential-explanatory design framework shows two strands, with the data collection and analysis from the quantitative and qualitative strands. By mixing both quantitative and qualitative research and data, the researcher gained an in-depth understanding after corroboration while offsetting the weaknesses inherent in using each approach by itself. **Mixing Procedures.** Given the two separate phases, the design required a substantial length of time to complete all data collection. The main purpose of mixing quantitative and qualitative data is for the

qualitative data to help explain the quantitative data. Thus, quantitative and qualitative data were connected. Mixed methodologies were observed in the formulation of the purpose, research questions, and integration of data in the findings and interpretation of the study. A data integration technique was applied to establish either the complementation of quantitative and qualitative data or the sequential connection between these two data sets. The qualitative data either confirms or contrasts the quantitative findings. Either of these citations of the previous studies, explained the results. In addition, the specific research questions of the study served as a guide in interpreting the results. The mixing was done to better understand the influence of parental academic support on student reading motivation. Figure 2 shows the study's systematic procedure. It demonstrates the use of a sequential-explanatory mixed methods design, where quantitative and qualitative data were corroborated to determine the influence of parental support on learners' reading motivation. Then, after adequate time, the responses to the survey questionnaires were conducted using Google Forms, which were encoded and analyzed. Concurrently, IDI and FGD were conducted in the selected elementary public schools in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. In the quantitative strand, the participants' responses to the validated survey questionnaire were analyzed using computer applications, and the answers were numeric data as the output. In addition, appropriate statistical tools, including mean, Pearson r , and multiple regression, were used to analyze the quantitative data. After analysis, the data was presented according to the sequence of the research problems. In the qualitative data strand, the researcher purposefully selected the participants for the IDI and FGD. The IDI and FGD schedules were set at the participants' convenience. Every detail of the responses was taken into consideration, but those that were not relevant to the study were not reflected. In addi-

tion, the interview proceedings were recorded with the participants' consent. Thematic analysis was employed, consisting of six phases. The researcher started by transcribing, reading, and re-reading the data, and then initial codes or features were created. The next phase was searching for the themes and collating the codes. As to integrating the quantitative and qualitative results phases, the researcher interpreted and explained the quantitative and qualitative results to arrive at a very substantial discussion, implications, and recommendations. The researcher determined a logical sequence for data collection activities, considering factors such as research objectives, study design, and ethical considerations. Sequential data collection methods may have been employed, with quantitative data collection preceding qualitative data collection or vice versa, depending on the research design. For instance, the researcher first administered surveys or questionnaires to gather quantitative data on their perception related to authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers. Subsequently, qualitative data collection methods such as interviews or focus group discussions have been conducted to explore participants' experiences, perceptions, and attitudes in greater depth. In the emphasis stage, the researcher may have emphasized certain aspects of data collection based on the research objectives and the level of importance assigned to different variables or themes. For instance, the researcher have emphasized data collection related to gender identity and its influence on knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. Lastly, the mixing procedures involve integrating quantitative and qualitative data collection methods to enhance the overall data collection process and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic. The researcher has used a mixed methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques to triangulate findings and corroborate results.

3. Results and Discussion

This reflects the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of findings. Specifically, this chapter reveals both quantitative and qualitative data relevant to addressing the research questions formulated in Chapter 1. The tabulated quantitative findings are presented in Tables 1-12, while the qualitative findings are organized in Tables 3. Table 13 shows the nature of data integration between quantitative and qualitative results.

3.1. Parental Academic Support in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte—Table 1 shows the summary on the extent of parental support. It is shown in the table that in totality, the extent of parental academic support in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte has an overall mean of 3.67 described as extensive. It means that the the extent of emotional and physical support that is given by the parents to the student in relation to their academic life is oftentimes manifested by the teachers in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. The cited overall mean score was the result obtained based on the mean score of 3.62 or extensive for time students spend with their parents, 3.71 or extensive for parents' involvement in school, and 3.67 or extensive for parents' ways of discipline. The extensive rating on parental academic support denotes that emotional and physical presence of the parents, and being consistently dependable for the students in times of their academic needs is oftentimes evident. This finding is congruent to the result of the study of Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) that students are likely to achieve higher grades and academic success when they receive consistent support and encouragement

Fig. 1. Flow of Procedures

from their parents. Also, the result supports the assertion of Delgado (2020) that parental involvement fosters a sense of self-worth in stu-

dents, as they feel valued and supported in their educational endeavors.

Table 1. Parental Academic Support in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Time Students Spend With Their Parents	3.62	Extensive
Parents' Involvement in School	3.71	Extensive
Parents' Ways of Discipline	3.67	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.67	Extensive

3.1.1. Parents' Involvement in School—This domain of parental academic support in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte reveals a category mean of 3.71 described as extensive. In particular, the mean ratings in this category, as shown in appendix A, ranges from 3.61 to 3.78. It shows that the item, misbehaving in class (refer to Appendix A) has a mean of 3.61 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed among the respondents in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. Meanwhile the item, participating in school programs (refer to Appendix A) has a mean of 3.78 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed. The result implies that the extent of the methods utilizes by the parents to reinforce a certain behavior of a child is oftentimes observed among the respondents in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. This finding is the same with the findings of Pineda et al. (2018) that extensive parents' involvement allows for stronger parent-teacher relationships. This collaboration can lead to better insights into the child's strengths, weaknesses, and learning style. Also, the result agrees with Pinantoan (2013) that schools with active parental involvement tend to have higher graduation rates as students feel supported and motivated to stay committed to their education. When parents demonstrate the importance of education through their involvement, it can in-

still a love for learning in children, encouraging them to become lifelong learners.

3.1.2. Parents' Ways of Discipline—In this domain, parents' ways of discipline reflect a category mean rating of 3.67, described as extensive. The items in this category reflect mean ratings from 3.50 to 3.78 (refer to Appendix A). Particularly, the item, texting all the time (refer to Appendix A) has a mean rating of 3.50 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed. meanwhile the item, failing to do household chores (refer to Appendix A) has a mean of 3.78 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed. The result implies that the activities and behaviors parents engage in at school, such as attending parent-teacher conferences and attending school events is oftentimes observed in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. This is congruent with the view of Owen (2016) that parenting style employed by the parents affect their relationship with their children. If parents are too strict or too lax to relate with their children, the performance of children in the school might as well be affected. Strict parents may hinder their children from sharing their difficulties in school. According to Adibsereshki et al. (2015) that the way parents discipline their children can influence their behavior in school. In the educational processes, positive reinforcement is considered as a com-

plex exercise.

3.1.3. *Time Students Spend with their Parents*—This domain reveals a category mean of 3.62 described as extensive. In particular, the mean ratings in this category range from 3.60 to 3.65 (refer to Appendix A). It shows that the item, finding it difficult to understand the world (refer to Appendix A) has a mean of 3.60 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed. Meanwhile the item having difficulties in school (refer to Appendix A) has a mean of 3.65 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed. This implies that the quality time spend by the parents with their children in relation to academic tasks of is oftentimes observed among respondents in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. This is congruent with the view of Parker and Wang (2013) that parents who think they spend the right amount of time with their children are about three times as likely as parents stating that they spend little time with their children to say their parenting job is excellent.

3.2. *Reading Motivation of the Senior High School Students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte*—It is shown in Table 2 that the extent of reading motivation of senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao

del Norte, has an overall mean rating of 3.68, which is described as extensive. As shown in the table, students’ reading motivation in terms of extrinsic academic compliance acquired the highest mean score of 3.71, described as extensive. Meanwhile, students’ reading motivation in terms of extrinsic test compliance acquired the lowest mean score of 3.66, also described as extensive. The result means that learners approach reading with enthusiasm and excitement. They genuinely enjoy the process of reading and are eager to explore new books or texts. This finding is congruent to the view of Hussain et al. (2020) that motivated readers are curious and open to exploring a wide range of genres, topics, and styles. They are not afraid to leave their comfort zones to discover new reading material. Also, the result supports Mahadi and Jafari’s (2012) assertion that individuals with high reading motivation often engage in independent reading, where they voluntarily choose and read books or articles without external prompting or requirements. Likewise, this corroborates with the idea of Alhamdu (2015) that students with high reading motivation are willing to invest time and effort in reading. They are persistent in finishing books and committed to making reading a regular part of their lives.

Table 2. Reading Motivation of Senior High School Students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Intrinsic Motivation	3.69	Extensive
Extrinsic Drive to Excel	3.65	Extensive
Extrinsic Academic Compliance	3.71	Extensive
Extrinsic Test Compliance	3.66	Extensive
Extrinsic Social Sharing	3.70	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.68	Extensive

3.2.1. Extrinsic Academic Compliance—This domain has a category mean of 3.71, which is described as extensive. The item in this category obtained mean ratings within the range of 3.62 to 3.83 (refer to Appendix A). Particularly, the item, It is important for me to receive a good grade in my English reading course (refer to Appendix A) has a mean rating of 3.62 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested. Meanwhile the item, Working harder on English reading assignments when they are graded (refer to Appendix A) has a mean of 3.83 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested by the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. The result denotes that the extent of compliance and consciousness for grades is oftentimes manifested among the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. This finding supports the proposition of Chinappi (2015) pointed out that extrinsically motivated students due to compliance tend to share what they read with other students, outperform other students, and aim to please their parents. In other words, extrinsic reading motivation is reading motivation because of external reasons. In extrinsic academic compliance, include the reason of students to read in foreign language just as the form of their responsibilities in reading classes. More so, Risinger (2013) noted that reading motivation literature suggests that compliance is a statement of outcome and indicates achievement of a goal identified in a reading-related tasks.

3.2.2. Extrinsic Social Sharing—This domain has a category mean of 3.70 described as extensive. Notably, the items in this category obtained mean ratings ranging from 3.62 to 3.79 (refer to Appendix A). The item, My friends and I like to share what we read in English (refer to Appendix A) has a mean of 3.62 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested. Meanwhile the item, Trying to read in English so I can understand what my

friends are talking about (refer to Appendix A) has a mean rating of 3.79 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested. The result implies that the extent of sharing of their experiences with others is oftentimes manifested by the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. This finding supports the proposition of Camacho-Minuche, Espinosa-Celinica, and Ulehlova (2021) that extrinsic social sharing can motivate students to read more actively as they seek to participate in conversations and share their reading experiences with others. Engaging in discussions and sharing about books can deepen students' understanding of the material. When they share their insights with others, it reinforces their own comprehension. Also, the result agrees with Gillies (2016) that sharing reading experiences can foster connections among students who share similar interests, promoting a sense of community and friendship.

3.2.3. Intrinsic Motivation—This domain reveals a category mean of 3.69 described as extensive. In particular, the mean ratings in this category range from 3.59 to 3.80 (refer to Appendix A). The item, Liking it when the topic of an English reading makes me think a little more (refer to Appendix A) has a mean of 3.59 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested. Moreover, the item Reading difficult English material more easily when the assignment is interesting (refer to Appendix A) has a mean of 3.80 described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested. The result means that strong internal drive and enthusiasm an individual experiences when engaging in an activity solely for its inherent satisfaction, pleasure, or personal interest is oftentimes manifested. This finding supports the view of Ahmadi (2016) intrinsically motivated students are willing to learn and have high interest in learning activity even without any reward because it come from their own desire. Also, the result agrees with Cherry (2020) that individuals with

high intrinsic motivation feel a sense of autonomy and control over their actions and choices. They are internally driven and self-directed in pursuing the activity. Those with high intrinsic motivation are often motivated by a desire to improve their skills and mastery in the activity. The process of learning and becoming better at the task is inherently rewarding.

3.2.4. Extrinsic Test Compliance—This domain on extrinsic test compliance garners a mean category of 3.66 described as extensive. In particular, the means of the items in this category range from 3.64 to 3.71 (refer to Appendix A). Adding on, the item on Trying to read in English because I like seeing my reading score improve on tests (refer to Appendix A) shows a mean of 3.64, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Trying to read in English because I need a good score on tests (refer to Appendix A), has a mean of 3.71, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested. This implies that the senior high school students' desire to gain scores on English standardized tests is oftentimes manifested in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. This finding supports Desta's (2020) view that grades are a factor that can impact academic motivation in students and can even create a fear of failure. Grades motivate students because they are a way to determine which people in a group are objectively most intelligent. Extrinsic Drive To Excel. This domain on the extrinsic drive to Excel garners a mean category of 3.66, described as extensive. In particular, the means of the items in this category range from 3.54 to 3.74 (refer to Appendix A). Adding on, the item on Thinking about how well I read compared to others when I read (refer to Appendix A) shows a mean of 3.54, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Wanting to be the best at reading (refer to Appendix A) has a mean of 3.74, described as extensive, interpreted as

an item oftentimes manifested among the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. This implies that the desire of students to improve their second language reading ability is oftentimes manifested. This finding supports the proposition of Steinmayr et al. (2019) that extrinsic motivation to excel in reading can lead individuals to set specific reading goals and strive to achieve them. They may be motivated to read more books, tackle more challenging texts, or improve their reading comprehension to earn rewards or recognition. Likewise, the result supports the idea of Sarangi (2015) that extrinsic motivation can push individuals to go beyond their comfort zones and dedicate more time and effort to reading. This can result in improved reading skills and higher levels of academic achievement.

3.3. Significant Relationship Between Parental Academic Support and Students' Reading Motivation in San Isidro District Davao del Norte—The results of the analysis on the relationship between parental academic support and students' reading motivation in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 11 shows the relationships between parental academic support and students' reading motivation in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. It shows that parental academic support has a significant positive relationship with the students' reading motivation with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .882$, $p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the parental academic support changes, the reading motivation of the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte, also significantly changes. Moreover, the table shows that parental academic support in terms of time students spend with their parents; parents' involvement in school; and parents' ways of discipline

have significant positive relationships with the students' reading motivation with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .901, p < 0.05$), ($r = .788, p < 0.05$), and ($r = .934, p < 0.05$), respectively. The current study's findings denote a significant relationship between parental academic support and reading motivation of the learners in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. Affirming that the reading motivation of senior high school stu-

dents is related to parental academic support. The finding further emphasized that increasing parental support improves the reading motivation of senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. This supports the achievement motivation theory by Atkinson and McClelland (1953), which explains the influence of the motive to achieve and the motive to avoid failure in a situation where performance is evaluated against some standard of excellence.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between Parental Academic Support and Reading Motivation of Senior High School Students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte

Indicators of Parental Academic Support	r-value	p-value	Decision
Time Students Spend With Their Parents	0.901*	0.000	Reject H0
Parents' Involvement in School	0.788*	0.000	Reject H0
Parents' Ways of Discipline	0.934*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall	0.882*	0.000	Reject H0

**Significant at $p < 0.05$*

3.4. —Standpoints of the Participants on the Quantitative Results Regarding the Extents of Parental Academic Support and Reading Motivation of Senior High School Students Table 4 presents the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the extensive ratings on parental academic support and reading motivation of senior high school students. From the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the extensive rating of parental academic support, three emerging codes identified namely: educational expectations; role modeling; and concern for child's future.

3.4.1. *Educational Expectations*—Parents with high expectations are often more willing to allocate resources to support their child's education. This may include investing in tutoring, educational materials, extracurricular activities,

and technology to enhance learning. The result implies that when parents have high educational expectations for their children, it can motivate the students to excel in their studies. The desire to meet their parents' expectations can be a powerful incentive to work hard and perform academically. The result is congruent with Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) 's view that high expectations can also translate into emotional support. Parents may offer encouragement, praise, and a sense of pride when their children meet or exceed academic goals, which can boost a child's self-esteem and motivation. Parents with high expectations are more likely to participate in their child's education actively. They may attend parent-teacher conferences, communicate with teachers regularly, and participate in school activities to ensure their child is on track.

3.4.2. Role Modeling—Parents who prioritize education and learning send a clear message to their children about the value of knowledge and the importance of continuous learning. The result means that when parents are actively engaged in their own educational pursuits or have successful academic and professional backgrounds, they can serve as sources of inspiration for their children. Children often look up to their parents and are more likely to value education when they see their parents doing the same. The result supports the view of Delgado (2020) that parents who have succeeded in their academic and professional endeavors may set high expectations for their children's educational achievement. These expectations can act as a motivating factor for students to strive for excellence. Parents who have experienced the challenges of education firsthand are often more equipped to provide effective academic support. They may offer guidance, resources, and assistance with homework, projects, and study strategies.

3.4.3. Concern for Child's Future—Concerns for a child's future often translate into a strong emphasis on the importance of education. Parents stress the value of learning as a means to secure better opportunities and outcomes in life. This indicates that when parents are deeply concerned about their child's future, they often become highly motivated to ensure their child's success in education. This motivation can lead to increased involvement and support in their child's academic journey. This supports the assertion of Pineda et al. (2018) that parents who are concerned about their child's future are more likely to allocate resources to support their education. This may include investing in books, tutoring, educational programs, and extracurricular activities to enhance their child's learning. Parents with future concerns often engage in long-term planning for their child's educational and career goals. They work with their children to set objectives and map out strategies to

achieve them. On the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the extensive rating on reading motivation of senior high school students, there were three emerging reasons that identified namely: personal interest and passion; choice and autonomy; and peer influence.

3.4.4. Personal Interest and Passion—Many senior high school students have developed a genuine interest and passion for reading. They've discovered specific genres, authors, or topics that they find intriguing and enjoyable. The result implies that personal interest and passion encourage students to explore diverse genres and subjects. They are more likely to seek out new and challenging books to satisfy their curiosity and expand their knowledge. Reading becomes a source of pleasure and relaxation for students. They often look forward to spending time with a good book, making it an enjoyable and fulfilling leisure activity. The result is congruent to the view of Alhamdu (2015) that when students have a genuine personal interest and passion for a particular genre, author, or topic, their motivation to read is primarily driven by internal factors. They read because they enjoy it, not solely for external rewards or requirements.

3.4.5. Choice and Autonomy—High school students often have more autonomy in choosing their reading materials. When they have the freedom to select books that align with their personal interests, it can boost their motivation. Choice and autonomy empower students to take ownership of their learning. The result means that autonomy encourages students to explore diverse genres, authors, and subjects. They may venture into areas they wouldn't have considered otherwise, broadening their reading horizons. Students can read at their own pace, allowing for a comfortable and enjoyable reading experience. This reduces the pressure to keep up with a standardized reading schedule. The result supports Carroll and Fox's (2017) idea that when students have

the freedom to choose their reading materials, they are more likely to select texts that align with their interests, experiences, and curiosity.

3.4.6. *Peer Influence*—Positive peer influence can also play a role. If students have friends who enjoy reading and share their enthusiasm for books, it can create a reading culture within the group. The sense of camaraderie and shared interest in reading can significantly influence their reading motivation. This indicates that peer recommendations can introduce students to new books and genres they might not have discovered on their own. When friends

suggest interesting reads, it can inspire students to explore a wider range of literature.

The result supports the assertion of Chinnappi (2015) that when students see their peers excited about reading, it creates a positive and motivating environment. They are more likely to view reading as an enjoyable activity worth investing their time in. Friendly competition among peers can be a motivating factor. When students compete to read more books or engage in reading challenges, it encourages them to read more and keep up with their peers.

Table 4. Standpoints of the Participants on the Quantitative Results Regarding the Extents of Parental Academic Support and Reading Motivation of Senior High School Students

Essential Theme	Reasons
Confirmed Extensive Rating on Parental Academic Support	Educational Expectations
	Role Modeling
	Concern for Child’s Future
Confirmed Extensive Rating on Reading Motivation of Senior High School Students	Personal Interest and Passion
	Choice and Autonomy
	Peer Influence

3.5. *Standpoints of the Participants on the Significant Relationship Between Parental Academic Support and Reading Motivation of Senior High School Students*—Table 5 presents the participants’ standpoints on the quantitative results regarding the significant relationship between parental academic support and reading motivation of senior high school students. Three emerging codes were identified: homework assistance, expectations and values, and emotional support.

3.5.1. *Homework Assistance*—Parents who offer help with homework and school-

related tasks can reduce stress and frustration in students. This support can make students feel more confident in their academic abilities and more motivated to engage in reading and other academic activities. The result implies that when parents help their children with homework, they can explain complex concepts or unclear instructions, leading to a better understanding of the reading material. This improved comprehension can make the reading experience more enjoyable and motivating. Parents can support the development of essential reading skills, such as comprehension and critical

thinking, which are essential for enjoying and engaging with texts. As students become more proficient readers, they may find reading more motivating. This supports the view of Wang and Sheikh-Khalil (2014) that homework assistance can help students overcome challenging aspects of their assignments, reducing frustration. When students don't struggle as much with their homework, they are more likely to approach reading with a positive attitude.

3.5.2. Expectations and Values—When parent's express high expectations for their children's academic performance and emphasize the importance of education, students are more likely to internalize these values and take their studies, including reading, more seriously. This implies that parents who set high expectations for their children's academic performance, including reading, send a clear message that education is a priority. Students are more likely to be motivated to meet these expectations to gain their parents' approval and achieve academic success. This supports the findings of Jung and Zhang (2016) that expectations from parents create a sense of accountability in students. They feel responsible for their academic progress, which includes reading. This accountability motivates them to complete their reading assignments and perform well. Parents who instill values emphasizing the long-term benefits of education and reading help students see the bigger picture. Students are motivated by the

idea that their efforts in reading will lead to personal growth, knowledge, and success in the future.

3.5.3. Emotional Support—A supportive and nurturing family environment can enhance students' self-esteem and emotional well-being. When students feel secure and loved, they are more likely to be motivated to engage in various activities, including reading. The result implies that emotional support provides a safe and nurturing environment where students feel comfortable discussing their academic concerns and fears. Students who are less stressed and anxious are more likely to approach reading with a positive attitude and motivation. This supports the idea of Núñez et al. (2015) that parents who provide emotional support boost their children's self-esteem and confidence. When students feel valued and validated, they become more confident in their abilities, including their reading skills. This increased confidence can lead to higher reading motivation. Emotional support fosters a positive and supportive learning environment at home. Students who feel emotionally secure are more likely to engage in academic activities, such as reading, with enthusiasm and motivation. When parents provide emotional support, students are less afraid of failure. They know that they have a safety net and a source of comfort to turn to if they encounter difficulties in their reading.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusion and recommendation. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were by statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—This study aimed to determine the influence of parental support towards the reading motivation of the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte, using mixed methods, specifically the sequen-

tial explanatory design wherein adapted survey questionnaires were used in the quantitative phase and through in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD) in the qualitative phase. On one hand, in the quantita-

Table 5. Standpoints of the Participants on the Significant Relationship Between Parental Academic Support and Reading Motivation of Senior High School Students

Essential Theme	Reasons
Confirmed Significant Relationship Between Parental Academic Support and Reading Motivation of Senior High School Students	Homework Assistance Expectations and Values Emotional Support

tive phase of the study, adapted survey questionnaires were used to gather data from the learners of public elementary schools to determine the significance of the influence of teaching parental support on the reading motivation of the learners. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The study’s findings show that parental academic support in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte, has an overall mean of 3.67 and a descriptive rating of extensive. Parental academic support in terms of time students spend with their parents, parents’ involvement in school, and parents’ ways of discipline obtained mean scores of 3.62, 3.71, and 3.67, respectively. The reading motivation of the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte, has an overall mean of 3.68 and a descriptive rating of extensive. Students’ reading motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic drive to excel, extrinsic academic compliance, extrinsic test compliance, and extrinsic social sharing obtained mean scores of 3.69, 3.65, 3.71, 3.66, and 3.70, respectively. Pearson Moment Correlation Analysis shows that parental academic support has a significant positive relationship with the reading motivation of the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than

.05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .0.882$, $p < 0.05$). It indicates that as parental academic support increases, the reading motivation of senior high school students also increases. From the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the extensive rating of parental academic support, the three emerging reasons are as follows: educational expectations, role modeling, and concern for the child’s future. From the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the extensive rating on reading motivation of senior high school students, the three emerging reasons are as follows: personal interest and passion, choice and autonomy, and peer influence. From the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the significant relationship between parental academic support and reading motivation of senior high school students in San Isidro District in Davao del Norte, the three emerging reasons are as follows: homework assistance, expectations, and values; and emotional support.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: Parental academic support in San Isidro District in Davao del Norte was rated as extensive. Parental academic support in terms of time students spend with their parents, parents’ involvement in school, and parents’ ways of discipline acquired extensive ratings. This implies that the emotional and physical presence

of the parents and their consistent dependability for the students in times of their academic needs were often observed. Second, the extent of reading motivation of the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte, was rated as extensive. Reading motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic drive to excel, extrinsic academic compliance, extrinsic test compliance, and extrinsic social sharing acquired an extensive rating. This means that learners approach reading with enthusiasm and excitement. They genuinely enjoy the process of reading and are eager to explore new books or texts. Parental academic support has a significant positive relationship with the reading motivation of the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte. This means that as the extent of the parental academic support changes, the reading motivation of the senior high school students in San Isidro District, Davao del Norte, also significantly changes. The quantitative results on the extensive parental academic support were further substantiated by reasons (educational expectations, role modeling, and concern for the child's future) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The quantitative results on the extensive reading motivation of senior high school students were further substantiated by reasons (personal interest and passion; choice and autonomy; and peer influence) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The quantitative results on the significant relationship between parental academic support and reading motivation of senior high school students in San Isidro District in Davao del Norte were further substantiated by reasons (homework assistance; expectations and values, and emotional support) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data,

generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The salient quantitative and qualitative findings revealed a parallel result. The corroborated finding means that the quantitative and qualitative findings merged and connected.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: Parental academic support was rated as extensive but may be raised higher if the school administrator implements an in-service training program for teachers to develop their skills in dealing with parents and other stakeholders. This may help develop teacher-parent collaboration, especially during the distance learning approach amidst the pandemic. Through this, parents may be encouraged to continuously support their children by participating in different training and activities offered by the school to equip them with knowledge and skills to support their children and help them improve their academic performance at school. A school-based program for enhancing the reading motivation of senior high school students through extensive training in vocabulary learning strategies for students may be implemented. This program may be facilitated by different stakeholders such as teachers, community leaders, and parents, since it was found that parental involvement was a significant mediator of the relationship between vocabulary learning strategy and reading motivation. The program aligns with implementing the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10533). The Department of Education adopts the enclosed Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program. Future studies may also include further analysis of the same study, with the inclusion of moderating variables such as age, gender, socio-economic status, and grade level. These may affect the mediating effect of parental academic support.

5. References

- Ahmadi, R. M. (2016). The impact of motivation on reading comprehension.
- Alahmadi, A., Shank, C., & Foltz, A. (2018). Vocabulary learning strategies and vocabulary size: Insights from educational level and learner styles. *Vocabulary Learning and Instruction*, 7(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.7820/vli.v07.1.alahmadi>
- Alhamdu. (2015). Interest and reading motivation. *PSIKIS-Jurnal Psikologi Islami*, 1(1), 1–10.
- Alimohammadi, N., Jafari-Mianaei, S., Hasanpour, M., Banki-Poorfard, A. H., & Sadat Hoseini, A. S. (2017). Parents' role before and during infancy: An islamic perspective. *Iranian Journal of Neonatology*, 8(4), 65–73. https://ijn.mums.ac.ir/article_9981.html
- Alqurashi, N. (2013). Vocabulary learning strategies of saudi undergraduate efl students at taif university and its relation to their vocabulary size [Unpublished MA Thesis, Anglia Ruskin University].
- Alyami, M., & Mohsen, M. A. (2019). The use of a reading lexicon to aid contextual vocabulary acquisition by efl arab learners. *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*, 48, 1005. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10936-019-09644-z>
- Anderson, T. L. (2015). *Examining elementary students' use of electronic readers for independent reading* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Tennessee, Knoxville]. https://trace.tennessee.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2447&context=utk_graddiss
- Anjomshoa, L., & Sadighi, F. (2015). The importance of motivation in second language acquisition. *International Journal on Studies in English Language and Literature (IJSELL)*, 3(2), 126–137. <https://www.arcjournals.org/pdfs/ijSELL/v3-i2/12.pdf>
- Antipkina, I., & Ludlow, L. H. (2020). Parental involvement as a holistic concept using rasch/guttman scenario scales. *Journal Psychoeducational Assessment*, 38, 846–865. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0734282920903164>
- Aregu, B. (2013). A study of self-regulated learning strategies as predictors of critical reading. <http://www.academicjournals.org/journal/ERR/article-full-text-pdf/0C9999D41499>
- Astuti, S. P. (2013). Teachers' and students' perception of motivational teaching strategies in an indonesian high school context. *TEFLIN Journal*, 24(1), 14–31. <http://journal.teflin.org/index.php/journal/article/view/152>
- Azar, A. S., & Tanggaraju, D. (2020). Motivation in second language acquisition among learners in malaysia. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 7(2), 323–333. <http://jurnal.unsyiah.ac.id/SiELE/article/view/16506>
- Babae, N. (2012). Motivation in learning english as a second language: A literature review. *Canadian Journal for New Scholars in Education*, 4(1), 1–7. <https://journalhosting.ualgary.ca/index.php/cjnse/article/view/30496/24887>
- Baharudin, H., & Ismail, Z. (2014). Vocabulary learning strategies and arabic vocabulary size among pre-university students in malaysia. *International Education Studies*, 7(13), 219–226. <http://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/ies/article/view/43620>
- Bailey, T. (2017). *The impact of parental involvement on student success: School and family partnership from the perspective of students* [Doctoral dissertation] [Doctor of Education in Teacher Leadership]. https://digitalcommons.kennesaw.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1023&context=teachleaddoc_etd

- Bas, G., & Beyhan, O. (2019). Revisiting the effect of teaching of learning strategies on academic achievement: A meta-analysis of the findings. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science (IJRES)*, 5(1), 70–87. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1198049.pdf>
- Bobis, J., Anderson, J., Martin, A., & Way, J. (2012). A model for mathematics instruction to enhance student motivation and engagement. In D. Brahier (Ed.), *Motivation and disposition: Pathways to learning mathematics* (pp. 31–42). National Council of Teachers of Mathematics.
- Boonk, L., Gijsselaers, H. J., Ritzen, H., & Brand-Gruwel, S. (2018). A review of the relationship between parental involvement indicators and academic achievement. *Educational Research Review*, 24, 10–30. <https://library.parenthelp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/35-A-review-of-the-relationship-between-parental-involvement-indicators-and-academic-achievement..pdf>
- Bramucci, A. (2013). Self-regulated learning: Theories and potential applications in didactics. http://intelligent-tutor.eu/files/2012/06/I-TUTOR_supportmaterial_self-regulated-learning_EN.pdf
- Brown, C., Danvers, K., & Doran, D. (2016). Student perceptions on using guided reading questions to motivate student reading in the flipped classroom. *Accounting Education*, 25(3), 256–271. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09639284.2016.1165124>
- Brown, H. D. (2014). *Principles of language learning and teaching*. Pearson Education.
- Butt, D., & Unsworth, L. (2016). The impact of intrinsic motivation on reading comprehension. *International Journal of Educational Psychology*, 5(2), 169–192. <https://doi.org/10.17583/ijep.2016.2013>
- Byrne, D. (2010). *Teaching and researching writing*. Longman.
- Cameron, L., & Dwyer, E. (2012). Parent involvement in student reading: A review of the literature. *Australian Journal of Language and Literacy*, 35(3), 281–296. <https://www.alea.edu.au/cms/parent-involvement-in-student-reading-a-review-of-the-literature-0>
- Carson, K., Cormier, J., & Gunasekara, A. (2016). The role of parental involvement in the success of students in reading comprehension. *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 6(1), 32–40. <http://www.macrothink.org/journal/index.php/ijld/article/view/9190>
- Chaudhry, I. S., & Firdous, H. (2016). Impact of parental involvement on academic performance of secondary school students. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(21), 1–7. <https://iiste.org/Journals/index.php/JEP/article/view/32362>
- Chen, L., Wang, J., & Zhan, J. (2015). The relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of preschool children: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 73, 22–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2015.06.002>
- Chen, X. (2012). *Parental involvement in children's learning: A cross-national study of the importance of context*. Springer.
- Chong, S. Y., Tan, H. T., & Tan, J. Y. (2019). Effects of parental involvement on students' motivation and engagement in learning: A systematic review. *Educational Psychology Review*, 31(3), 321–346. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-018-9455-5>
- Clayton, M., Luthy, M., & Becker, J. (2019). The role of parental involvement in enhancing student performance in english language arts: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of*

- Research in Education and Science*, 5(2), 318–330. <https://www.ijres.net/index.php/ijres/article/view/492>
- Colbert, S., Risen, J. L., & Chae, C. (2015). The effects of teacher-student relationships on student engagement and academic achievement. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 27(1), 56–64.
- Dalal, H., & Rehman, A. (2017). Motivation in language learning: A study of 12 learners in pakistan. *Asian Journal of Research in Education and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 65–75. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327267830_Motivation_in_Language_Learning_A_Study_of_L2_Learners_in_Pakistan
- Demir, S., & Hidroğlu, M. (2019). The influence of parental involvement on students' motivation and achievement in efl classroom. *International Journal of Learning and Teaching*, 5(1), 33–38. <http://www.ijlt.org/index.php/IJLT/article/view/40>
- Dewar, K., & Skinner, T. (2015). *The role of motivation in the development of self-regulated learning: A longitudinal study*. Springer.
- Dixon, J., & Earle, A. (2017). The role of teachers in supporting parental involvement in children's education. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 25(4), 341–356. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669760.2017.1342578>
- Doan, T. T., & Vinh, L. Q. (2018). Impact of parental involvement on the academic performance of high school students: Evidence from vietnam. *Journal of Educational Sciences*, 2(2), 74–85. <http://www.ejournal.unri.ac.id/index.php/JES/article/view/891>
- Duong, V. T., Phan, T. H., & Nguyen, T. L. (2020). Parental involvement and academic performance of high school students: Evidence from vietnam. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 99, 101511. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.101511>
- Dyson, L., & Khairuddin, Z. (2019). A longitudinal study of parental involvement and student academic achievement in mathematics. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 95, 111–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.06.005>
- Elemen, A. (2016). The impact of parental involvement on students' academic achievement in high school. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 108(3), 431–440. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000095>
- Engelmann, H., & Roeser, R. W. (2020). The role of parental involvement in the academic achievement of students in primary and secondary schools: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 32, 93–116. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-019-09469-0>
- Engle, L., Russell, R., & Slater, M. (2015). Parental involvement and academic achievement: A meta-analytic review. *Review of Educational Research*, 85(3), 451–480. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654314558495>
- Feldman, D. H., & Seligman, M. E. P. (2012). *The relationship between parental involvement and students' academic achievement*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Francisco, D., Karp, K., & Lovett, L. (2018). Parental involvement and its influence on children's academic performance. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 6(10), 1–12. <http://www.ijern.com/journal/2018/October-2018/35.pdf>
- Gonzalez, C., Szymanska, K., & Wichowski, M. (2020). Parental involvement, academic achievement, and motivation of children in early childhood education: A systematic review. *International Journal of Child Care and Education Policy*, 14(1), 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40723-020-00085-5>

- Gonzalez, J., Ainscow, M., & Bennett, N. (2018). Parental involvement and children's school engagement: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 24, 15–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2018.03.001>
- Hamre, B. K., & Pianta, R. C. (2017). Classroom climate and developmental relationships between children and teachers: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 109(8), 1059–1071. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000160>
- Harari, H., & Sadeh, A. (2018). Parental involvement and students' academic performance: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 30(3), 647–669. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-018-9445-7>
- Hodge, K., & Wright, M. (2020). Parental involvement and students' academic success: A meta-analysis of the relationship between parental involvement and student achievement. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 99, 101518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.101518>
- Horn, I. S., & Kane, R. (2017). Parental involvement and children's learning: A systematic review. *Review of Educational Research*, 87(4), 859–899. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654317714573>
- Hsiao, Y. C., & Liu, Y. M. (2020). The impact of parental involvement on students' motivation and academic achievement in english as a foreign language learning. *International Journal of Learning and Teaching*, 6(1), 44–50. <http://www.ijlt.org/index.php/IJLT/article/view/73>
- Huynh, H., & Cheng, C. (2020). The influence of parental involvement on students' academic achievement in vietnam: A systematic review. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 99, 101516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.101516>
- Jensen, J., & Rask, K. (2017). Parental involvement and student motivation: A systematic review. *Educational Psychology Review*, 29(2), 295–314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-016-9370-0>
- Karakus, M., & Hersi, A. (2020). The effects of parental involvement on students' academic success in turkey: A systematic review. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 99, 101513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.101513>
- Kim, K. H., & Frick, M. (2019). The impact of parental involvement on children's achievement in early childhood education: A meta-analysis. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 46, 25–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2018.07.005>
- Kim, Y., & Hill, N. R. (2015). The role of parental involvement in children's academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 27(4), 597–618. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-015-9320-1>
- Klug, J., & Dinsmore, D. L. (2020). Parental involvement and academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 32(1), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-019-09451-8>
- Konstantopoulos, S., & Hedges, L. V. (2016). Teacher quality and student achievement in the early grades: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(4), 971–1011. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654315623099>
- Langevine, J. A. E. (2020). *Parental involvement and academic achievement of middle school: Hispanic american students in south texas* [Doctoral dissertation, Grand Canyon University].

- Laurillard, D. (2012). *Teaching as a design science: Building pedagogical patterns for learning and technology* [E-book]. Routledge.
- Legg, T. (2019). Intrinsic motivation: How to pick up healthy motivation techniques.
- Liu, P. L., & Lin, C. (2016). Mobile english vocabulary learning based on concept mapping strategy. *Language Learning & Technology*, 20(3), 128–141. https://scholarspace.manoa.hawaii.edu/bitstream/10125/44485/1/20.03_liu.pdf
- Liu, S., & Zhang, Y. (2018). Parental involvement and students' academic performance: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 30(3), 627–646. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-018-9433-y>
- Liu, Y., Sulaimani, M. F., & Henning, J. (2020). The significance of parental involvement in the development in infancy. *Journal of Educational & Practices*, 10(1), 161–166. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1268016.pdf>
- Llamas, A. V., & Tuazon, A. P. (2016). School practices in parental involvement, its expected results and barriers in public secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Science and Research*, 6(1), 69–78. https://www.academia.edu/23703434/SCHOOL_PRACTICES_IN_PARENTAL_INVOLVEMENT_ITS_EXPECTED_RESULTS_and_BARRIERS_IN_PUBLIC_SECONDARY_SCHOOLS
- Long, C., Ming, Z., & Chen, L. (2013). The study of student motivation on english learning in junior middle school: A case study of no.5 middle school in gejiu. *English Language Teaching*, 6(9), 136–145. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1077185.pdf>
- Maccoby, E. E., & Martin, J. A. (2016). Socialization in the context of the family: Parent-child interaction. *Handbook of Child Psychology*, 3, 1–101. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119125556.chfam003>
- Manyak, P., Von Gunten, P., Autenrieth, D., Gillis, C., & O'Farrell, C. (2019). Four practical principles for enhancing vocabulary instruction. https://www.ccgedu.net/uploads/8/5/6/8/85683126/four_practical_principles.pdf
- Mata, L., Pedro, I., & Peixoto, F. J. (2018). Parental support, student motivational orientation and achievement: The impact of emotions. *International Journal of Emotional Education*, 10(2), 77–92. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1197565>
- Mathewson, T. R. (2019). How to unlock student's drive for learning? <https://hechingerreport.org/intrinsic-motivation-is-key-to-student-achievement-but-schools-kill-it/>
- Maulana, R., Opdenakker, M., Stroet, K., & Bosker, R. (2013). Changes in teachers' involvement versus rejection and links with academic motivation during the first year of secondary education: A multilevel growth curve analysis. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 42(9), 1348–1371. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-013-9921-9>
- McLeod, J., & Smith, M. (2019). Parental involvement and children's academic achievement: A systematic review. *Educational Psychology Review*, 31(1), 3–33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-018-9443-9>
- Miles, T. S. (2016). *A case study on parent's perceptions of their role in the educational process* [Doctoral dissertation, Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies]. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3235&context=dissertations>
- Morgan, D. N., & Wagner, C. W. (2016). What's the catch? providing reading choice in a high school classroom. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 56(8), 659–667. <https://doi.org/10.1002/JAAL.193>

- Moskovsky, C., Arabai, F., Paolini, S., & Ratcheva, S. (2013). The effects of teachers' motivational strategies on learners' motivation: A controlled investigation of second language acquisition. *Language Learning*, 63(1), 34–62. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9922.2012.00717.x>
- Moukarzel, M., Noun, R., & Njeim, R. (2016). Parental involvement and academic performance: A review of the literature. *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 6(2), 33–40. <http://www.macrothink.org/journal/index.php/ijld/article/view/9183>
- Muliati, C. (2017). The students' motivation in reading and reading interest of the fifth semester students of iain palangka raya. <http://digilib.iain-palangkaraya.ac.id/813/1/Skripsi%20Chitra.pdf>
- Mwirichia, V. M. (2013). Influence of parental involvement on academic performance of preschool children in kangeta division, meru county, kenya. http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/11295/63060/Mwirichia_Influence%20of%20parental%20involvement%20on%20academic%20performance.pdf?sequence=3
- Nicolai, R., Miehle, J., & Beck, H. P. (2019). Parental involvement in education: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 26, 30–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2019.100282>
- Nisiforou, E. A., & Laghos, A. (2015). Do the eyes have it? using eye tracking to assess students cognitive dimensions. *Educational Media International*, 50(4), 247–265. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09523987.2013.862363>
- Norman, E. (2020). Why metacognition is not always helpful? *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 15–37. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7346872/>
- Ntekane, A. (2018). Parental involvement in education. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324497851>
- Núñez, J. C., Suárez, N., Rosário, P., Vallejo, G., Valle, A., & Epstein, J. L. (2015). Relationships between perceived parental involvement in homework, student homework behaviors, and academic achievement: Differences among elementary, junior high, and high school students. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 108(5), 525–536. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2015.1004611>
- O'Connor, R. E., & McCartney, K. (2017). Parental involvement in early education: Home and school predictors of academic achievement in early childhood. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 109(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000094>
- Ogunsola, S. O. (2020). Parental involvement and student academic performance: A comparative analysis of public and private schools in nigeria. https://www.academia.edu/45693535/Parental_Involvement_and_Student_Academic_Performance_A_Comparative_Analysis_of_Public_and_Private_Schools_in_Nigeria
- Orr, A., & Shute, V. J. (2020). Parental involvement and academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(2), 111–143. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654319892491>
- Özdemir, M., & Çakiroglu, J. (2014). Motivational strategies used by english teachers in high school: A case study of two teachers. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 14(2), 715–722. <http://www.edam.com.tr/eng/doi.php?id=JESTP-14132>
- Phunwong, S., & Khamkhien, A. (2018). Parental involvement in learning and educational achievement of the students: A case study of the phetchaburi school, thailand. *Interna-*

- tional Journal of Educational Science and Research*, 8(4), 1–14. http://www.academia.edu/38245878/Parental_involvement_in_learning_and_educational_achievement_of_the_students_A_case_study_of_the_Phetchaburi_School_Thailand
- Pomerantz, E. M., & Wang, Q. (2012). The role of parental involvement in children's academic achievement: A longitudinal study. *Developmental Psychology*, 48(2), 344–359. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0026683>
- Quarles, C. S., & Williams, R. L. (2017). The relationship between parental involvement and the academic achievement of middle school students in the united states. *International Journal of Educational Science and Research*, 7(1), 23–34. https://www.academia.edu/34786094/The_Relationship_Between_Parental_Involvement_and_the_Academic_Achievement_of_Middle_School_Students_in_the_United_States
- Rangel, A. (2020). Parental involvement in education: A research perspective. https://www.academia.edu/42696723/Parental_Involvement_in_Education_A_Research_Perspective
- Roberts, K. L., & McFadden, L. H. (2019). Parental involvement and student achievement: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 99, 101517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.101517>
- Robinson, C., & Zhang, Y. (2017). Parental involvement in homework: What do parents really do? *International Journal of Educational Research*, 84, 29–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2017.06.006>
- Rodriguez, S. C., & Sanchez, M. J. (2020). Parental involvement and its influence on students' academic achievement: A case study in puerto rico. *Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, 26(2), 153–168. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339435588_Parental_Involvement_and_its_Influence_on_Students'_Academic_Achievement_A_Case_Study_in_Puerto_Rico
- Sadiq, A., & Zafar, M. (2021). Parental involvement and academic achievement of students in pakistan: A meta-analysis. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 41(1), 58–73. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2020.1762673>
- Shariati, M., & Ebrahimi, M. (2019). The relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of high school students in iran. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 97, 24–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.06.001>
- Sheldon, S. B., & Epstein, J. L. (2018). Parental involvement in student achievement: A meta-synthesis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 30(3), 541–562. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-018-9438-6>
- Silva, P. S., Ferreira, J. C., & Santos, L. F. (2020). The role of parental involvement in children's education: A study of the primary school. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 112(4), 710–723. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000384>
- Smith, J., & Smith, L. (2017). Parental involvement and students' academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 87(3), 622–654. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654317701374>
- Stevens, R., & Van De Walle, J. (2018). How does parental involvement in education affect academic achievement? *American Educational Research Journal*, 55(3), 481–508. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831218770430>
- Tadesse, S., & Almaz, M. (2020). Parental involvement and students' academic performance: A review of the literature. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 8(4), 79–96. <https://www.ijern.com/journal/2020/April-2020/06.pdf>

- Thompson, B., & Simmons, A. (2021). The relationship between parental involvement and student academic performance in primary education: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(4), 1411–1433. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09608-8>
- Trinidad, A., & Martin, G. (2020). Parental involvement and academic performance: Evidence from primary schools in manila. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(11), 25–33. <https://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/JEP/article/view/50187>
- Villalobos, A. M., & Villalobos, E. E. (2020). Parental involvement and academic performance of preschool children: A comparative analysis of urban and rural settings in mexico. *International Journal of Education Research*, 20(1), 57–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2020.07.002>
- Wang, M., Wei, W., & Han, Z. (2021). Parental involvement and children’s academic achievement: A meta-analysis of studies conducted in china. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(3), 953–982. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-021-09606-7>
- Wang, M. T., & Sheikh-Khalil, S. (2017). Effects of parental involvement on school engagement and early adolescent achievement: Longitudinal findings from the early adolescence study. *Child Development*, 88(1), 77–90. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12605>
- Wong, S., & Cheung, C. (2020). Parental involvement and student engagement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 32(3), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09515-7>
- Yang, Y., & Hu, Y. (2020). Parental involvement and academic achievement: A meta-analysis of studies conducted in china. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(1), 211–234. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09554-1>
- Yazdani, A., & Jafari, A. (2019). Parental involvement and students’ academic performance: A meta-analysis of literature in iran. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 101, 18–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.02.002>
- Zhang, H., Zhang, Y., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Parental involvement and academic achievement: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(2), 379–404. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09573-y>
- Zhao, X., & Chen, R. (2019). Parental involvement and academic achievement: A meta-analysis of studies conducted in china. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 97, 11–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.06.003>
- Zhou, H., & Ma, Z. (2021). Parental involvement and students’ academic achievement: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(4), 1151–1175. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09602-x>